
Green Synthesis and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles from *Tectona grandis* Leaf Extracts

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ABSTRACT

Silver nanoparticles have garnered particular attention among the many noble metal nanoparticles because of their exceptional qualities, which include suitable electrical conductivity, chemical stability, catalytic activity, and antibacterial activity. Silver at the nanoscale has shown entirely different characteristics from bulk particles of the same material due to its high surface to volume ratio. This study, investigated the synthesis of green nanoparticles using extracts from Tectona grandis Leaf. The nanoparticles were characterized using UV-visible spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, X-ray diffractometer (XRD), Scanning electron microscope (SEM) - Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Characterization studies indicated that Tectona grandis nanoparticles exhibited dark brown coloration with strong UV-visible absorption peaks at 420 nm. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of hydroxyl, carbonyl, alkene, and amine functional groups. SEM microscopy revealed predominantly spherical or oval nanoparticle morphology. XRD analysis established the presence of silver with a defined crystalline structure. The Leaf extracts act as a reducing agent for nanoparticles synthesis, which consequently established the bioprocess with the advantage of being environmentally friendly.

KEY WORDS: Characterisation, *Tectona grandis*, Green Synthesis, Nanoparticles, Bioprocess

INTRODUCTION

Nano biotechnology is an upcoming field of research where plants and plant extracts are used for the synthesis of nanoparticles (Das *et al.*, 2023). Nanoparticles have a strong tendency to clump together, forming larger clusters known as agglomerates. This characteristic is particularly valuable for creating surface coatings on metals. The unique properties of nanoscale particles are mainly due to their high surface area and large surface area-to-volume ratio (Yiu-Wing and Zhong-Zhen, 2006). Nanotechnology is emerging as a promising solution to the corrosion problem, offering an alternative to traditional, often harmful, and costly chemical inhibitors. While numerous studies have explored the connection between an inhibitor's structure and its effectiveness, research investigating the influence of molecular size and electrical distribution on protection efficiency remains comparatively limited. Thin films with thicknesses in the micron and nanometer ranges are becoming more and more popular in scientific and technological applications due to the quick development of nanotechnology. Nanoparticles are high in the ratio of their surface area to volume in contrast to particles that are micronized; this very characteristic makes them effective corrosion inhibitors (Atta *et al.*, 2013). Nanoscale extraction can be achieved using a variety of renewable sources, such as plant materials, insects, and microorganisms (Singh *et al.*, 2017).

Teak, or *Tectona grandis*, is a large deciduous tree prized for its wood, which is used to craft furniture, cabinets, and musical instruments. Known for its large, shiny leaves with hairy undersides, teak belongs to the *Lamiaceae* family. While primarily valued for its timber, the tree also offers potential medicinal benefits. Its flowers and seeds are considered diuretics, while the wood is believed to have laxative and sedative properties for the uterus. Additionally, teak bark has been traditionally used to treat diabetes and bronchitis. Its leaves, bark, and wood show antioxidant properties, with wood showing a maximum of 98.6% inhibition against DPPH (Das *et al.*, 2023).

Tectona grandis has been the subject of intensive phytochemical study and chemical component isolation. Several studies have revealed the presence of several groups, including tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, anthraquinones, and naphthoquinones, which contain atoms such as O and N and functional groups that can help limit corrosion (Ashvin and Rajaram, 2014).

Silver nanoparticles have garnered particular attention among the many noble metal nanoparticles because of their exceptional qualities, which include suitable electrical conductivity, chemical stability, catalytic activity, and antibacterial activity (Vijay Kumar *et al.*, 2014). Silver at the nanoscale has shown entirely different characteristics from bulk particles of the same material due to its high surface to volume ratio. (Thirunavoukkarasu *et al.*, 2013). As a result, Ag NP synthesis is a fascinating and developing field. Ag NPs are produced in a variety of sizes and shapes for use in a wide range of applications utilizing a variety of physical, chemical, and biological processes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs)

The Ag NPs were synthesized following the procedure described in Pratap *et al.* (2014) and Rautela *et al.* (2019). The experiment involved mixing 90 ml of a dilute 1 mM silver nitrate solution (prepared with double-distilled water) with 10 mL of an extract from the *Tectona*

grandis samples. The mixture was brought to a near boil and continuously agitated at high speed (800 rpm) using a special stirring device (a magnetic stirrer). The formation of a dark brown color indicated nanoparticle (NP) synthesis. The mixture was spun in a centrifuge for 30 min at 4000 rpm. This separated the solid material (like settling dust) from the liquid. The solid was then washed thoroughly with water to remove any unwanted substances. Finally, it was dried at 60°C and stored in a container that keeps moisture out. This prepared the material for further testing of its properties and its ability to prevent corrosion.

Characterisation of *Tectona grandis* silver nanoparticles

UV-Visible spectrophotometer

The bio-reductant of the silver nanoparticles was monitored by UV– visible (UV–vis) spectrum at various time intervals. The UV–vis spectra of this solution were recorded from 200 to 800 nm. A Genesys 10 S UV-Visible spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance. Scanning was between 200 and 800 nm.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

An Agilent Technologies FTIR spectrophotometer was used to analyze the functional groups present in the extract and silver nanoparticles. The scan range was from 600 to 4000 cm^{-1} . The dried samples of the extract and silver nanoparticles were grounded with KBr pellets and analysed.

X-ray diffractometer (XRD)

The synthesised nanoparticles were characterised to reveal their crystal structure using X-ray diffraction technique (XRD). The XRD pattern was recorded using computer controlled XRD-system (Model Rigaku Mini-Flex II) with CuK α radiation (Ni filtered = 1.5406 Å°) in the range of 40 kV, 30 mA. The built-in software (syn master 7935) program was used for the identification of XRD peaks corresponding to the Bragg's reflections.

SEM-EDX analysis technique

A scanning electron microscope (Phenom Pro X Model no: 800-07334) was used to examine the shape and overall structure of the tiny silver nanoparticles. The Samples were prepared by depositing a drop of the colloidal solution on an aluminum grid sample holder.

Additionally, a technique called (energy) dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was used to identify the elements in the particles, confirming the presence of silver.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles

Visual observation

A visual observation revealed that the *Tectona grandis* (TG) -incubated silver nitrate displayed a deep brown color. The deep brown color is an obvious sign that Ag nanoparticles were formed. As reported by Salaudeen *et al.* (2021), the formation of colour is a result of

excitation of surface plasmon vibrations in the Ag nanoparticles (Salaudeen *et al.*, 2021). The development of Ag nanoparticles in the solution is shown by this colour shift (Godwin *et al.*, 2022). The apparent hue shift supported the Ag⁺ reduction. This shift in hue denotes the creation of Ag nanoparticles in the solution as a result of the silver nanoparticles' surface plasmon vibration being excited (Godwin *et al.*, 2022).

UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-vis)

The observed UV-visible spectra for TG Ag NPs are presented in Figure 1. According to the literature, green synthesis produced silver nanoparticles with absorbance values between 418 and 448 nm in the visible range (Awad *et al.*, 2010; Ahmed *et al.*, 2016; Alsammarraie *et al.*, 2018). From the absorption spectrum, three peaks can be observed at 337.4, 420, and 674 nm. The prominent peak at 420 nm indicates the formation of Ag NPs because it falls within the range of the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) for Ag NPs. The absorbance value obtained in this study is close to the work of Ahmed *et al.*, (2016) who obtained an absorbance value of 445 nm for the synthesis of Ag NPs from *Azadirachta indica* aqueous leaf extract. The other two peaks may be due to some components in the crude extract of *Tectona grandis*.

Figure 1: UV-visible absorption spectrum of TG silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs)

Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FT-IR) Analysis

The FT-IR spectra of TG Ag NPs is shown in Figures 2. The extract and synthesized nanoparticles consist of certain functional groups which range from 3280.1 cm^{-1} to 890.83 cm^{-1} for TG Ag NPs, the functional groups correlate to OH at 3280 cm^{-1} , C=C at 1524 cm^{-1} , C=O at 1732 cm^{-1} , C-H at 1028 cm^{-1} for TG NPs. The functional groups, to which the nanoparticles are attached serve as reducing and capping agents for the silver nanoparticles. According to the literature, proteins and amino acid residues' carbonyl groups have a greater capacity to bind Ag NPs, preventing agglomeration and stabilizing of the Ag NPs through free amine groups in proteins (Emeka *et al.*; 2014; Shanka *et al.*, 2014; Agbaje *et al.*, 2016; Supraja *et al.*, 2020). The extracts and nanoparticles, according to these data, consist of (O-H, C=O, C=C, and N-H) atoms in functional groups that satisfy the requirements of a typical corrosion inhibitors.

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of TG Ag NPs

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy dispersive x-ray (SEM-EDX) analysis

The produced particles were round and oval in shape, as shown by the SEM images. A small number of individual particles were also visible, although the majority of the nanoparticles were aggregated. The particles were well dispersed, an indication of good stability against aggregation. The EDX pattern showed that silver was the predominant element present in the Ag NPs solution (Alsammorraie *et al.*, 2018; Rautela *et al.*, 2019). The profiles of SEM-EDX are displayed in Figure 3 for TG NPs.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs and (b) EDX Spectrum of TG Ag NPs

X-ray diffraction (XRD) Analysis

Figure 4 shows the X-ray diffraction pattern, which confirms the crystalline structure of the silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) synthesized using the leaf extract. This analysis of the dried nanoparticles, originally dispersed in a colloidal solution, further strengthens the evidence of their crystalline nature. The face-centered cubic (FCC) crystalline structure of TG silver is confirmed by the peaks in the X-ray diffraction pattern of the TG silver nanoparticles, which correspond to the Bragg's reflections of the (101), (200), (220), and (311) planes for the synthesized TG Silver nanoparticles. Based on the (FCC) structure of TG silver nanoparticles, XRD investigation revealed strong peaks at 2θ values of 37.35° , 46.20° , 54.29° , 56.24° , 77.82° corresponding to Bragg's reflection. A distinct broadening of the XRD peaks suggests that the material that has been manufactured contains particles within the nanoscale range. This demonstrates unequivocally that the TG's reduction of Ag^+ ions to Ag^0 produced silver nanoparticles, which are crystalline in nature (Merajuddin *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 4: XRD Spectrum of TG Ag NPs

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a simple, safe, and one-step process was utilized for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles using the *Tectona grandis* Leaf extracts, the Leaf extracts act as a reducing agent for nanoparticles synthesis. No chemical reagent was used in the process, which consequently established the bioprocess with the advantage of being environmentally friendly

RECOMMENDATIONS

Tectona grandis nanoparticles exhibited a good inhibition efficiency and, as such, can be used as eco-friendly inhibitors for mild steel. Further long-term Stability and performance of the Ag NPs inhibitors should be explored.

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